

Collaborative Governance in Handling the Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) Pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City

Muhammad Rofi'ud Muta'al¹, Prof. Dr. Winarti, M.Si², Drs. Joko Suranto, M.Si.³

^{1, 2, 3}State Administration Science, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences Universitas Slamet Riyadi Surakarta

ABSTRACT: Indonesia is one of states affected by Covid-19 pandemic. Government has taken various attempts and made many policies to overcome Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia. Surakarta city is one of cities located in Central Java Province with high distribution rate. Mangkubumen sub district being the location of research is one of Sub District with the relatively low number of positive cases compared with some other sub district and has achieved zero cases in certain months in 2021. The objectives of research are to describe and to analyze the measures the Mangkubumen Sub District has taken in collaboration to overcome Covid-19 pandemic. The method used in this research was descriptive qualitative one, analyzed using Technique of Analyzing Data according Huberman and Saldana (2014:14). The management of Covid-19 pandemic Mangkubumen sub district was analyzed using Collaborative Governance theory suggested by De Seve (2007:50), consisting of eight indicators: Network Structure, Trust among the participants, Governance, Access to authority, Distributive accountability, Information sharing, and Access to resources. From the result of research, it can be concluded that the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen sub district ran successfully, based on Collaborative Governance indicator.

KEYWORDS: Collaborative Governance, Covid-19 Management, Role of Sub-District

INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 is a global problem specified as pandemic by World Health Organization (*WHO*) on March 11, 2020 because it has spread and been confirmed in 189 states. The spread of Covid-19 virus in Indonesia occurs firstly on March 2, 2020. Indonesian government has issued various policies in the attempt of overcoming Covid-19 pandemic occurring. Some policies have been made by the government to solve the pandemic. One of the policies is to establish teamwork called taskforce from central to regional government level. The Covid-19 taskforce at central government level is led directly by the

Chairperson of BNPB (National Agency for Disaster Management), Lieutenant General Doni Monardo. In addition to establishing the teamwork, Central government also conducted decentralization, the delegation of authority to regional government. Surakarta City, being the location of research, is one of cities in Central Java with high distribution of Covid-19 cases. Regional government is the element mostly responsible for the covid19 management in its region. The regional head is required to make technical decision that cannot be in contradiction with the central government regulation. One of programs launched by Central Java Regional Government is *Jogo Tonggo*. *Jogo Tonggo* was instructed by Central Java Governor through Governor's Instruction No. 1 of 2020 to be applied to City/Regency existing in Central Java Province that was then adjusted by Mayor/Regency.

Surakarta city becomes one of cities to keep attempting to overcome Covid-19 pandemic. The government of Surakarta city has issued various policies, one of which is to accelerate massive vaccination program for all people of Surakarta City. As a result, Surakarta City becomes one of cities with highest vaccination rate in Indonesia, 92.5% out of 417.151 people being the target, as released by the official website of Surakarta City. In addition, through Surakarta Mayor's Circular Number 067/495 about The Implementation of Microbased Community Activity Restriction and the Optimization of Sub District Taskforce in controlling the spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) in Surakarta City. Surakarta mayor also optimized this Covid-19 management role up to Sub District level. Thus, the Sub District existing in Surakarta City also plays an important role in helping the government overcome Covid-19 in Surakarta.

Mangkubumen sub district being the locus of research is one of Sub Districts located in Surakarta City, with the relatively low number of positively confirmed case, compared with other sub districts. Covid-19 Management Acceleration Taskforc of Surakarta City at <https://covid.intip.surakarta.go.id/> reported 350 positive cases per October 4, 2021 in Kelurahan Mangkubumen. This figure tends to be lower than that in Nusukan, Pajang, Sumber, Kadipiro, and Jebres Sub District (> 1000 positive cases).

Figure 1. Ratio of Covid-19 positive case number in some

Source: <https://covid.intip.surakarta.go.id/>

The head of Sub District Mangkubumen, in his interview with the author on October 7, 2021, confirmed that there has been no Covid-19 positive case in his region. The Sub District Mangkubumen's success in avoiding its region from Covid-19 and in reducing positivity rate is inseparable from the contribution of parties external to the Sub District in the attempt of implementing the governmental policy or called *collaborative governance*. Considering the result of interview conducted by the author, the components involved in Covid-19 pandemic management in Sub District Mangkubumen are: Sub District, community members affiliated with *jogo tonggo* taskforce, city government, in this case, the Health Office represented by Puskesmas (Public Health Center), and TNI (Indonesian Army) and Polri (Indonesian Police) through *Babinsa* and *Babinkamtibmas*. Collaborative Governance, according to La Ode (2018 : 4), is a type of governmental order encouraging collective attempt taken by stakeholders and non-governmental components to cooperate in solving complex problems through collective decision making and policy implementation. Considering the elaboration above, it can be said that Collaborative Governance is very important to optimizing the government policy in both policy making and implementation. Similarly, it is also important in the attempt of managing Covid-19 pandemic at Sub District level constituting the starting point of city government among the needy people and applying *Collaborative Governance* strategy.

METHOD

This research employed a descriptive empirical research with qualitative approach. Descriptive method, according to Moh. Nazir (2012: 54), is the one used to investigate a group of people, an object, a set of conditions, a thinking system, or a class of events in the present. Meanwhile, qualitative research by Sugiyono (2010 : 9) is defined as the one in which the author is positioned to be key instrument, data collection is done by combining several data, and data analysis is inductive in nature. Thus, it can be concluded that a descriptive qualitative approach is a research procedure using descriptive data, the one in written or spoken forms obtained from observable people or actors. The description and the facts of an event obtained are analyzed, interpreted, and presented systematically according to the actual condition based on the information and object studied.

Data analysis in this research was conducted using an interactive model of analysis according to Miles Huberman and Saldana (2014:14). In this analysis model, there are four components of analysis: data collection, data condensation, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification. The activities are conducted in interactive form through the process of collecting data as a sustainable, repetitive, and continuous process, thereby creating a cycle.

DISCUSSION

Collaborative Governance is an attempt and process implemented collectively by some actors outside the government in collaboration with government aiming to make or to implement public policy more effectively and efficiently. Referring to a theory suggested by De Seve (2007: 50), there are eight indicators in assessing collaboration in governance. They are:

1. Networked Structure

Networked structure explains the form of collaboration and synergy established by Government, community and others involved in the Covid-19 management in Sub District Mangkubumen. The clarity of collaboration form is very important to the performance of collaboration process, as it can give direction and guideline on how to implement and to distribute the task according to position and function. Those involved in pandemic management in Sub District Mangkubumen are Sub

Collaborative Governance in Handling the Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) Pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City

District, *Jogo Tonggo* Taskforce, Puskesmas (Public Health Center), BABINSA (Indonesian: *Bintara Pembina Desa* or noncommissioned law enforcement officer posted in villages), BABINKAMTIBNAS (Indonesian: *Bhayangkara Pembina Keamanan dan Ketertiban Masyarakat* or Community Police Officer), and SATLINMAS (*Satuan Perlindungan Masyarakat* or Community Protection Unit).

The network type of collaboration in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District belongs to Lead Organization type. Lead Organization, according to Milward and Provan is marked by the presence of administrative entity and likewise, manager that establishes network as the member of network/service provider. This model is more centralized in nature, compared with the Self-Governance model. It is categorized to be Lead Organization because based on the result of interview, there is an indicator of administrative entity presence, the chairperson of *Jogo Tonggo* Taskforce has clear administrative evidence in the form of Decree of Taskforce Officer Appointment given directly by *Lurah* (head of Sub District office) Mangkubumen. However, some other parties do not have MoU or written agreement. The form of synergy can be seen from the task division conducted, in which Sub District functions as facilitator and mobilizer in each of programs or activities implemented concerning the management of Covid-19 pandemic, but it also controls, monitors the isolation, tracing, and picking-up of patients. Meanwhile, *Jogo Tonggo* Taskforce serves as the facilitator of community members who undertake isolation related to their need. The *Puskesmas* officers serve to facilitate the tracing and testing process conducted, *BABINSA* and *BABIN KAMTIBMAS* serve to facilitate and to educate each of management process such as tracing, aid giving, isolation, etc. And *SATLINMAS* serves to help the implementation of management program. All parties participate actively in program implementation and coordination meeting as the form of collaboration between stakeholders. Technical guidance and training are also usually held by Puskesmas as the attempt of reinforcing the stakeholder institution.

2. Commitment to a common purpose

Commitment to a common purpose is collective objective and agreement between government, community and other parties involved in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District. Commitment to a Common Purpose usually involves Vision, Mission, and Objective in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District and also reinforces the collective objective in handling the Covid-19 pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District.

Considering the data existing, Mangkubumen Sub District does not have collective objective formulated jointly as intended in the theory. Despite no collective or common objective established directly to handle Covid-19 pandemic specifically in Mangkubumen Sub District, it has objective mentioned in Mayor's Circular Number 440/1439 of 2020, to take a community based attempt of accelerating the Covid-19 management by empowering all potencies existing systematically and in structured manner by considering:

- a. People wellbeing
- b. Environmental conduciveness and prevention of conflict among the people, to maintain the unity and integrity of the people
- c. Community Economic Condition
- d. Certainty of need fulfillment

The programs implemented in the attempt of improving collective understanding and reinforcing the collective objective included educating the people to live healthily, appealing to the people to take social distancing in worship places or in other places resulting in crowd. Then swab test should take swab test on the people who have positive or illness symptoms in Puskesmas (public health center) Manahan. In addition, the programs facilitate the implementation of both independent and centralized isolation programs and to trace the family members who live in the same houses where a positive individual lives and to give food staple aid to those undertaking independent isolation.

Those programs are not a program specific to or the innovation of Mangkubumen Sub District, because they have also been regulated in Standard Operating Procedure specified by City Government. However, the programs have been implemented actively with the people's contribution. In relation to this Commitment to a Common Purpose indicator, the management of Covid-19 pandemic has met the indicator of collective objective and reinforced the collective objective and agreement, because the presence of programs implemented as aforementioned can improve and to reinforce the capacity of office.

3. Trust among the participants

Trust among the participants is the form of professionalism and appropriate implementation of task by government, community and others involved in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District. Trust among the participants can be seen from the implementation of work program or policy by each of parties and appropriate time, cost, and target in the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic management program. Considering the data found in the field, the pandemic management program or activity has run smoothly and been appropriate-target in Mangkubumen Sub District; thus the case spread level has been zero case in October in this region.

Collaborative Governance in Handling the Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) Pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City

The case decreasing level occurs in May and October down to 0 (zero) case in Mangkubumen Sub District. It can reinforce the measurement of the performance of the Covid-19 pandemic management officers that have done their task smoothly and the full participation of parties professionally. In relation to the indicator of appropriate target, the implementation of pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District has been appropriate-target based on the result of data source triangulation indicating the same responses from the three informants interviewed.

4. Governance

Governance aspect includes transparency, accountability, and participation of government and those involved in Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District. Based on the data found in the field, viewed from transparency aspect, the government transparently gives the people access to the data of positively confirmed case number in Mangkubumen Sub District. People can access the data with easy procedure, by asking the heads of corresponding RT/RW or the officers in Sub District. Viewed from accountability aspect, all parties are responsible for reporting data or event occurring in Mangkubumen Sub District. Sub District is responsible for submitting the accountability report to City Government and Central Java Province, while *JogoTonggo* taskforce and Puskesmas also report to the Sub District, according to their own tasks. Then, *Babinsa* and *Babinkamtibnas*, despite not responsible for reporting to Mangkubumen Sub District, also helps indirectly the process of collecting data and collecting accountability. And people are also responsible for helping give self-help fund to the people who are undertaking independent isolation, but many people are not aware of and do not care about the implementation of health protocol. Viewed from participation aspect, people also participate in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District by joining *Jogo Tonggo* taskforce giving donation or attending social work (*kerja bakti*) in the region.

De Seve (2007: 50) states that a factor determining a successful network or collaboration is the clarity of good governance, including boundary and exclusivity, rules, Self determination, and Network management. Based on the result of interview and secondary data, out of the four points existing in the theory above, Pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District involves Boundary and exclusivity that can be evidenced by the officers doing the management task in restricted manner. Meanwhile, there is no clear rule related to membership, but there are some rules to regulate any actions taken. Meanwhile, Self determination and Network management have not been implemented firmly because it still refers to the rule or SOP specified. Thus, it can be concluded that in the indicator of governance certainty, according to De Seve theory, the four aspects have not been met fully.

5. Access to Authority

Access to authority is the authority and design of Covid-19 pandemic management process in Mangkubumen Sub District. It includes the availability of standards or measures of clear and acceptable procedure. Access to Authority includes the legal foundation of Covid-19 pandemic management, and standardization in Covid-19 pandemic management by the government. Considering the result of interview, there is a legal foundation of the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District, i.e. the Mayor's Circulars Number 440/1439 of 2020 about the Establishment of *Jogo Tonggo* Taskforce at Citizen Neighborhood (RW) level referring to the Governor Instruction Number 1 of 2020. In addition, there is standardization in the form of document to reinforce the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District, including the chart of management procedure according to the standard specified during technical guidance and the establishment and the procedure of coordination implemented by *Jogotonggo* Taskforce that has been standardized in Governor Instruction No.1 of 2021.

6. Distributive Accountability

Distributive accountability is the arrangement and the execution of management by those involved in Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District. *Distributive Accountability* includes the procedure of overcoming Covid-19 from preventing through following up the positive case, and from planning through evaluating the Covid-19 pandemic management policy program in Mangkubumen Sub District. Considering the result of interview, there is a procedure (SOP) regulating the Covid-19 pandemic management, particularly in Mangkubumen Sub District. The SOP is developed by Covid-19 Taskforce at Surakarta City level. The processes of planning, monitoring, and evaluating the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District were implemented collectively by all parties involved including Sub District, Satlinmas, Babinsa Babinkamtibnas, Puskesmas (public health center), and *JogoTonggo* Taskforce. The processes were implemented routinely and periodically either through whatsapp medium or directly in Pendopo Sub District or Sasono Krida of Mangkubumen People.

About 20 (twenty) SOPs have been made by the City Government, related to each of Covid-19 pandemic management activities existing. However, not all SOPs are delivered and distributed to the pandemic management at Sub District level, because some SOPs are intended specifically to city level only, for example: SOP of Mayor Regulation Development, SOP of Public Communication, etc. Thus, not all SOPs existing can be applied to Mangkubumen Sub District. Meanwhile, planning, monitoring, and evaluating processes have not been conducted consistently and as scheduled, due to the uncertain social restriction and to adapt to urgency or need for discussion.

Collaborative Governance in Handling the Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) Pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City

7. Information Sharing

Information sharing is an easy access to information and information management in the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District. Information sharing can be seen from the aspect of easy access to information for Mangkubumen people, coordination between stakeholders, and information and communication systems. Considering the result of interview, the information concerning the data of the number of people affected or positively confirmed has been shared to the people transparently by maintaining the privacy of the confirmed one. The sharing is conducted through RT (neighborhood association) and RW (Citizen, association) to be forwarded to the people. Information and communication processes among those involved in the Covid-19 management in Mangkubumen Sub District started with the information given by Puskesmas to Sub District and *JogoTonggo* Taskforce that later became the material to do the next management process. Another form of communication occurs in bottom-up manner, in which *JogoTonggo* Taskforce at RW level also reports the case and gives update data about its people to Sub District. Thus, communication may start with each of parties involved.

8. Access to Resources

Access to resources is related to the availability of human resource, financial resource and facilities and infrastructure owned to achieve an objective. *Access to resources* involves structural and field officers. Helpers/additional officers (community and private), budget, and facilities for those affected by Covid-19 are provided in the Covid-19 pandemic management policy or program. Considering the result of interview and the author's opinion, the human resources existing in this Covid-19 pandemic management are medical or health workers from *Puskesmas* (public health center) Manahan, *JogoTonggo* Taskforce members, Sub District Officers, tracers, and other officers like *Babinsa*, *Babinkamtibnas* and *Satlinmas*. Meanwhile, the financial resource in the Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District derives from Budget Fund (DPA) of Mangkubumen Sub District and other funding sources beyond the government, for example, the fund coming from the private like PMS and *IKA UNS*. Infrastructure resource includes facilities obtained by those affected with Covid-19 virus. Those with severe illness will get treatment for free in the referral hospital and those undertaking independent family isolation will get food staple aid from Social Office, Sub District Office, Community, and private.

CONCLUSION

The covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District of Banjarsari Sub District of Surakarta City can be considered as successful, based on Collaborative Governance aspect.

The indicators of successfulness are:

1. Network Structure

Type of collaborative structure applied to the context of Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District is *Lead Organization*. The form of synergy can also be seen from the task division conducted. There is an institutional reinforcement in the form of technical guidance and training.

2. Commitment to a common purpose

Mangkubumen Sub District does not have common purpose or objective formulated collectively as intended in the theory. However, the Covid-19 management in Mangkubumen Sub District has an objective included in Mayor's Circular Number 440/1439 of 2020. The reinforcement of objective and the improvement of understanding are also conducted by implementing some programs or activities with public participation.

3. Trust among the participants

There has been trust between the parties involved or participants, as indicated with the programs implemented successfully. The programs completed have been appropriate-target.

4. Governance

The process of managing the Covid-19 pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District has implemented transparency, accountability, and participation principles. Considering the four aspects of governance certainty according to De Seve's theory, in pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District, *Boundary* and *exclusivity* aspects have been met, but *Rule* aspect has not been met, and *Self-Determination* and *Network management* aspects have not been implemented firmly.

5. Access to authority

There is a legal foundation in the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen Sub District, Mayor's Circular Number 440/1439 of 2020, there is a standardization in the form of document to reinforce the implementation of Covid-19 pandemic management in Mangkubumen. Sub District

6. Distributive accountability

There are some procedures (SOPs) made by City Government to regulate the Covid-19 pandemic management. Meanwhile, planning, monitoring, and evaluating processes have not been conducted consistently and adjusted with the urgency of discussion.

Collaborative Governance in Handling the Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) Pandemic in Mangkubumen Sub District, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City

7. Information sharing

The sharing of information access to the people about the data of those infected by Covid-19 in Mangkubumen Sub District is done through Whatsapp medium. Communication and information process in the Covid-19 management in Mangkubumen Sub District among the participants starts with the information given by Puskesmas, while other communication form can start with those involved.

8. Access to resources

Human resource existing in this Covid-19 pandemic management includes medical workers, *JogoTonggo* Taskforce members, Sub District Officers, tracers, *Babinsa*, *Babinkamtibnas* and *Satlinmas*. Meanwhile, financial resource comes from Budget Fund (DPA) of Kelurahan Mangkubumen and other funding sources, such as the fund coming from self-help community fund or social grant. Infrastructure resource includes facilities available for the people infected by Covid-19 virus, in which those sick severely will get treatment for free in the referral hospital and those undertaking independent family isolation will get food staple aid.

REFERENCES

- 1) Alfiyanti, Yati. 2008. "Validitas Dan Reliabilitas Dalam Penelitian Kualitatif." *Jurnal Keperawatan Indonesia* Vol 12 No(2) hal 137-141.
- 2) Amin, Raja Muhammad, Rury Febrina, and Baskoro Wicaksono. 2021. "Handling COVID19 from a Collaborative Governance Perspective in Pekanbaru City." *Jurnal Bina Praja* 13(01): 1–13.
- 3) Ansell, Chris, and Alison Gash. 2008. "Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice." *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 18(4): 543–71.
- 4) B.D., Ratner. 2012. *Collaborative Governance Assessment*. Penang, Malaysia: CGIAR Research Program on Auatic Agricultural System.
- 5) Bila, Aziza, and Boni Saputra. 2019. "Collaborative Governance Strategy in Government Sector." *Jurnal Transformasi Administrasi* 9(2): 196–210.
- 6) De Seve, G Edward. 2007. *The Business of Government*. IBM Center for The Business of Government.
- 7) Dewi, Ratna Trisuma. 2012. "Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Collaborative Governance Dalam Pengembangan Industri Kecil." Universitas Sebelas Maret Durakarta.
- 8) Ekha, Roni, Tengku Rika, Putri Febri, and Nia Audina. 2020. "Collaborative Governance dalam Penanganan Penyebaran Kasus Corona Virus Disease-19 Di Kota Padang. In *Konferensi Nasional Ilmu Administrasi*, , 133–37.
- 9) Haryono, N. 2012. "Jejaring Untuk Membangun Kolaborasi Sektor Publik." *Jurnal Jejaring Administrasi Publik* 01.
- 10) Irawan, Denny. 2017. "Collaborative Governance (Studi Deskriptif Proses Pemerintahan Kolaboratif Dalam Pengendalian Pencemaran Udara Di Kota Surabaya)." *Jurnal Kebijakan dan Manajemen Publik* 5: 1–12.
- 11) Islamy, La Ode Syaiful. 2018. *Collaborative Governance Konsep Dan Aplikasi*. Yogyakarta: DeePublish (CV Budi Utama).
- 12) Miles, Huberman, and J. Saldana. 2014. *Qualitative Data Analysis, A Methods Sourcebook, Edition 3*. USA: Sage Publications. Terjemahan Tjetjep Rohindi Rohidi, UI-Press.
- 13) Muta'al, Muhammad Rofiud, and Aprilia Setyowati. 2021. "Strategi Collaborative Governance Pada Rangka Resiliensi Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19." In Slamet Riyadi Conference On Public Administration, , 21–36.
- 14) Nazir, Moh. 2012. *Metode Penelitian*. Bogor.: Ghalia Indonesia
- 15) Pramono, Joko, and Farco Siswiyanto Raharjo. 2020. "Kebijakan Taktis Pemerintah Daerah Di Pulau Jawa Dalam Penanganan Corona Virus Desiase (Covid)-19." *Jurnal Manajemen Publik & Kebijakan Publik* 2(2): 57–69.
- 16) Rivelino, Rivelino, and Arwanto Harimas Ginting. 2020. "Tata Kelola Kolaborative Dalam Kebijakan Publik Dari Perspektif Penanganan Covid -19 Dki Jakarta." *Jurnal Politik Pemerintahan Dharma Praja* 13(1): 36–51.
- 17) Sugeng Cahyono, Anang. 2021. "Implementasi Model Collaborative Governance Dalam Penyelesaian Pandemi Covid-19." *Jurnal Publiciana* 14(01): 83–88.
- 18) Sugiyono. 2010. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 19) Sutopo, H.B. 2006. *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*. Surakarta: Universitas Sebelas Maret Press.
- 20) Zaenuri, M, and T Sulaksono. 2015. "Pengelolaan Pariwisata-Bencana Berbasis Kolaboratif Governance (Studi Pariwisata-Bencana Lava Tour Merapi Di Kabupaten Sleman)." Research Repository UNY.
- 21) Surat Instruksi Gubernur Jateng No. 21 Tahun 2020, Tentang Percepatan Penanganan Covid-19 Satgas Jogo Rogo
- 22) Surat Edaran Walikota Surakarta Nomor 440/1439 Tahun 2020 tentang Pembentukan Satgas Jogo Tonggo di Tingkat Rukun Warga (RW).
- 23) <https://covid.intip.surakarta.go.id/> diakses pada Kamis, 9 September 2021